

Attachment avoidance predicts emotion-induced blindness

Steven J. Kirsh & Jeffrey R. W. Mounts
SUNY Geneseo (United States)

kirsh@geneseo.edu

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This study examined the relationship between adult attachment orientation and attentional bias to threat using an emotion-induced blindness paradigm. Emotion-induced blindness refers to reduced accuracy in identifying a neutral target when it appears shortly after an emotionally salient distractor, reflecting the capture of limited perceptual resources by emotional information. A total of 232 participants completed self-report measures assessing global attachment anxiety and attachment avoidance and then performed an emotion-induced blindness task involving threatening and non-threatening interpersonal images. The task required participants to identify the orientation of a neutral target image presented at varying temporal intervals following emotionally charged distractors. Regression analyses indicated that attachment avoidance, but not attachment anxiety, significantly predicted emotion-induced blindness following the presentation of threatening images. Specifically, higher levels of attachment avoidance were associated with poorer target identification at intermediate temporal lags, suggesting greater attentional capture by threat related stimuli. No significant effects were observed for attachment anxiety, or for the interaction between attachment anxiety and avoidance. These findings were specific to threatening content and did not emerge uniformly across all stimulus types or temporal intervals. The results are interpreted within the framework of the dual process model of avoidant attachment, which proposes an initial automatic attunement to threat followed by strategic attentional disengagement. The observed pattern is consistent with the notion that individuals high in attachment avoidance initially allocate attentional resources to threat related cues, leading to temporary impairment in processing subsequent neutral information. Over longer intervals, attentional resources may be released, allowing performance to recover. In contrast, the absence of effects for attachment anxiety suggests that hypervigilant processing may depend on contextual factors such as stress, which were not manipulated in the present study. Overall, the findings extend existing research on attachment related attentional processes by demonstrating that attachment avoidance is associated with selective impairments in perceptual processing under conditions of emotional competition.

Keywords: attachment avoidance; attachment orientation; attentional bias; emotion-induced blindness; threat

Starting in infancy, youth develop internal working models (i.e., mental representations) of their attachment figures' availability, sensitivity, and responsiveness. These person-specific mental representations are continually updated in order to reflect the current care they are receiving (Bowlby, 1982). Over time, individualised internal working models coalesce into a generalized representation of close relationships comprised of two primary dimensions: attachment anxiety and attachment avoidance (Fraley et al., 2011).

Attachment anxiety involves the hyperactivation of attachment-related thoughts, feelings, and behaviours. Individuals high in attachment anxiety consistently worry about rejection or abandonment while, at the same time, having a strong need to feel close to others. Additionally, they are posited to demonstrate an intense awareness of attachment-activating emotional cues and potential threats. In contrast, attachment avoidance refers to a pattern of attachment-related deactivation or disengagement, characterized by emotional distancing, suppression of negative affect, and a general distrust of others' availability and responsiveness. Thus, those high in attachment avoidance are thought to disregard or disengage from attachment-related information (Brennan et al., 1998; Mikulincer & Shaver, 2016). However, rather than disregarding emotionally-laden cues and threats in a singular process, Niedenthal et al. (2002) contend that avoidant individuals automatically attune to threat prior to attentional disengagement and avoidance (which result from controlled cognitive processes). Chun et al. (2015) posit that this type of two-stage processing decreases the likelihood that those high in attachment avoidance will fully attend to attachment-related information.

For those high in either attachment anxiety or attachment avoidance, failure to deploy their respective internal working model-based strategy of hyperactivation or automatic attunement followed by strategic disengagement may result in unwanted emotional discomfort or dysregulation. In contrast, for individuals low in both attachment avoidance and attachment anxiety (i.e., securely attached), there is relatively little need to pay close attention to the emotional cues and potential threats in their environment. They know that regardless of what they encounter, those with whom they are attached will meet their needs (Mikulincer & Shaver, 2019).

With regards to threat detection, support for the avoidance-based attunement/disengagement and anxiety-based hyperawareness strategies has been mixed, with some studies supporting these connections and others contradicting them (for a review, see Peng et al., 2023). To clarify these associations, Peng and colleagues conducted a meta-analysis of 68 studies that assessed the connection between attachment styles with attentional bias. Results indicated that individuals with high attachment avoidance paid little attention to emotionally-charged information (suggestive of a singular, rather than dual, process model). In contrast, the combination of being under stress and high attachment anxiety was linked with attentional vigilance towards attachment-related content. However, the articles included in the Peng et al. study assessed attentional bias through a variety of techniques, such as the dot-probe task, emotional Stroop task, eye-tracking, and others. Despite this robust combination of assessment tools, none of the studies reviewed assessed emotion-induced blindness -- a reduction in the correct identification of a neutral target image when it follows an emotionally charged distractor image (Most et al., 2005).

In the most commonly used emotion-induced blindness procedure, an emotionally charged image (e.g., depictions of violence) is presented within a rapid stream of neutral stimuli, including a target image that is rotated away from its canonical orientation. Participants are tasked with identifying the orientation of the rotated target image. Poorer performance in identifying the target's rotation following an emotionally charged image is called emotion-induced blindness (Most et al., 2005). Wang et al. (2012) contend that emotion-induced blindness occurs because perceptual processing resources are preferentially allocated to emotionally charged images, thereby impairing the representation of subsequent stimuli. Over time (i.e., with longer distractor-target intervals), these processing resources are disengaged from the emotional stimulus, and accuracy rates recover to baseline performance levels. Thus, the emotion-induced blindness task is well-suited to evaluate the extent and for which emotional stimuli capture attentional resources.

The purpose of the current study is to determine if global attachment avoidance and attachment anxiety are associated with the processing of attachment-related emotional cues and threatening stimuli. To address these issues, participants completed an emotion-induced blindness task involving images of violent and nonviolent interpersonal conflict presented at 3 lag points (200ms, 500ms, & 800ms). Our hypotheses regarding performance on the emotion-induced blindness task are

derived from the dual process model avoidance attachment. As such, it is expected that those with high attachment avoidance will demonstrate higher levels of emotion-induced blindness at earlier lag points (due to automatic attunement), but lower levels of emotion-induced blindness at later lag points (as a result of attentional disengagement). In contrast, it is hypothesized that those with high attachment anxiety will show evidence of EIB at both early and later lag points (reflective of hypervigilance).

METHOD

Participants

The participants were 232 undergraduate students ($M = 18.9$, $SD = 1.9$; 86% female; 83% White) from a midsize college in Western New York State. Participants were recruited from the psychology subject pool and received extra credit for their participation. A power analysis using G*Power (Faul et al., 2009) affirmed a minimum sample size of 77 participants for the intended analyses, given alpha at 0.05, a priori power at .80, and anticipated medium effect sizes.

Measures

Attachment orientation

Attachment orientation was assessed using the Relationship Structures questionnaire (ECR-RS; Fraley et al., 2011). The ECR-RS is a self-report measure designed to assess attachment anxiety and attachment avoidance in a variety of close relationships. Respondents are asked to indicate their level of agreement with relationship-based statements using a 7-item response scale (1 = strongly disagree; 7 = strongly agree). Whereas statements related to attachment avoidance focus on discomfort with closeness and interdependence, attachment anxiety statements address issues concerning separation, abandonment, and lack of care. The same nine items assess attachment to mothers, fathers, romantic partners, and best friends. Attachment anxiety and avoidance scales are created for each relationship target by averaging responses to like statements. Because we did not make predictions based on specific attachment relationships, we averaged responses to the attachment anxiety and attachment avoidance items across the four relational targets to create composite indices of global attachment anxiety and global attachment avoidance. The ECR-RS shows acceptable test-retest and composite reliability and structural validity (Fraley et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2021).

Emotion-induced blindness task

The emotion-induced blindness task was displayed on a Benq 24-inch monitor running at 100Hz using PsychoPy (Peirce et al., 2019). Participants were seated with their eyes approximately 60 cm from the monitor. All pictures used during the task were sized 28.4 cm by 21.3 cm on the screen and were full colour. The set of filler pictures consisted of 166 nature and city scenes that were absent people. The set of 85 target pictures was of similar content but in portrait format, allowing them to be rotated 90 degrees clockwise or anticlockwise, to yield the same aspect ratio as the other stimuli. Three categories of distractor images were used: neutral, conflict, and violent. Neutral pictures portrayed one or two people doing mundane tasks. Conflict pictures depicted nonviolent interpersonal conflict (i.e., two people arguing). Violent pictures included images of physical assault and people menacingly brandishing weapons. Each distractor set consisted of 54 pictures. All pictures were drawn from the International Affective Picture System (Lang et al., 2008) or freely available images from the Internet.

Participants completed eight practice trials and six blocks of 27 trials in the experimental task. The participant initiated each trial by pressing the down arrow on a keyboard. On each trial, a series of 18 pictures were presented one after the other in the centre of the screen, each for 100ms. Sixteen images presented in the sequence were drawn randomly without replacement from the filler set. Each of the three types of distractor pictures was presented equally often at slots 4, 6, and 8 of the sequence. No distractors were presented during the practice phase, and each distractor picture was used once during the experimental task. Target pictures were presented equally often at lags of 2 (200ms), 5 (500ms), and 8 (800ms) following the distractor. Four target pictures were randomly selected for practice; the remaining 81 targets were presented once at each of the two rotations during the experiment. Participants indicated the target's orientation using the keyboard's left and right

arrow keys. Participants received visual feedback following each trial regarding their accuracy, and they received summary feedback and were prompted to take a short rest every 27 trials.

Data exclusion

Twenty-three participants were excluded because they performed at lower-than-chance (50%) levels of accuracy on one or more conditions during the emotion-induced blindness task. As a result, the remaining sample consisted of 209 participants. No significant differences were evident between excluded and included participants on either global attachment anxiety or global attachment avoidance (all $p > .25$). Given the lack of differences, the generalizability of the study's findings should not be adversely affected.

Procedure

The authors obtained approval from the Institutional Review Board at the College. After signing the informed consent form, participants completed the demographic form and ECR-RS. Next, they completed the emotion-induced blindness task. At the end of the study, they were thanked and debriefed.

RESULTS

Preliminary Analyses

Correlations indicated significant negative associations between attachment avoidance and target discrimination following both violent ($r = -.18, p < .01$) and nonviolent interpersonal conflict ($r = -.13, p < .05$) images with a lag of 5. In addition, all lag points and picture types were positively correlated (all $p < .01$; see Table 1).

Table 1
Means, standard deviations, and correlations of attachment dimensions and accuracy of target detection

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. Attachment Anxiety	2.50	1.10	—										
2. Attachment Avoidance	2.60	0.90	.67**	—									
3. Conflict Lag 2	0.81	0.11	-.08	-.13	—								
4. Neutral Lag 2	0.82	0.12	.02	-.08	.53**	—							
5. Violent Lag 2	0.71	0.12	.04	.01	.31**	.36**	—						
6. Conflict Lag 5	0.86	0.10	-.07	-.16*	.45**	.39**	.25**	—					
7. Neutral Lag 5	0.86	0.09	-.00	-.08	.39**	.42**	.36**	.39**	—				
8. Violent Lag 5	0.84	0.11	-.12	-.18**	.48**	.43**	.34**	.40**	.33**	—			
9. Conflict Lag 8	0.86	0.10	-.05	-.11	.37**	.40**	.24**	.38**	.44**	.31**	—		
10. Neutral Lag 8	0.86	0.10	.04	.00	.44**	.38**	.25**	.33**	.46**	.32**	.33**	—	
11. Violent Lag 8	0.85	0.11	.04	-.04	.42**	.42**	.32**	.39**	.45**	.41**	.49**	.40**	—

Note. Attachment anxiety and avoidance were centred at the means

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

Multiple regression analyses

To test whether attachment orientation predicts emotion-induced blindness, we conducted a multivariate multiple regression analysis for nonviolent interpersonal conflict, neutral, and violent images at lags 2, 5, and 8, with attachment anxiety, attachment avoidance, and their interaction as predictor variables. Results indicated that attachment avoidance was negatively associated with target identification following the presentation of nonviolent interpersonal conflict images ($\beta = -.21$, $p < .03$) and violent images ($\beta = -.19$, $p < .05$), indicative of greater emotion-induced blindness for both picture types at lag 5. At lags 2 and 8, no significant effects were found for attachment avoidance. Both attachment anxiety and the attachment anxiety by attachment avoidance interaction failed to predict emotion-induced blindness at any of the three lags.

DISCUSSION

Results indicated a significant association between global attachment avoidance and emotion-induced blindness for both violent and nonviolent interpersonal conflict images. These findings contradict the contention that attachment avoidance is associated with diminished processing of attachment-related information (Mikulincer & Shaver, 2019). Nevertheless, they are generally supportive of the dual-process model of avoidant defences (Chun et al., 2015).

Chun and colleagues contend that those high in attachment avoidance engage in a two-stage process consisting of initial vigilance to threat followed by active avoidance of it. Regarding the current study, attachment information should capture the attention of avoidant individuals during the vigilance stage, resulting in emotion-induced blindness. During the avoidance stage, attention should actively disengage from the attachment stimuli, and target performance would return to baseline.

The pattern of performance observed in those with high attachment avoidance is consistent with the dual-process model. At lag 5 (500ms), those participants could still be in the first (attunement) stage, so continued processing of the distractor would hamper target performance. At lag 8 (800ms), they could have transitioned into the second (disengagement) stage, freeing processing resources for the target. It should be noted however, that the single-stream EIB task employed here does not allow us to conclude that the threat-related distractors are being actively suppressed by those with high attachment avoidance at lag 8. Given the speculative nature of this conclusion, more research is needed to discern when the shift from vigilance to avoidance occurs, and to confirm that active inhibition is occurring in the avoidance stage. Additionally, the connection between attachment avoidance and emotion-induced blindness was absent at Lag 2 (200ms). This is somewhat surprising given that 1) the effects of individual differences on emotion-induced blindness are frequently demonstrated at this lag (Onie & Most, 2022), and 2) theoretically, those high in attachment avoidance should already be demonstrating vigilance to threat. One possibility is that attachment-based attentional strategies are enacted later during processing, closer to 500ms. The precise time needed to engage in attachment-based attentional vigilance is an area for future research.

The association between attachment anxiety and emotion-induced blindness was nonsignificant. These findings contradict the contention that attachment anxiety is associated with a hypervigilant attentional strategy. Given that Peng et al. (2023) found that attachment anxiety only predicted attention bias when individuals are under duress, future research should involve stress-induction to see if a similar pattern develops for emotion-induced blindness.

Additionally, methodological differences may explain the inconsistency between Peng and colleagues' meta-analysis and findings of the current study. Whereas we assessed emotion-induced blindness, nearly 40% of the experiments reported in the Peng and colleagues' meta-analysis utilized the dot-probe task. In the dot-probe paradigm, participants are presented with a pair of stimuli on a computer screen (such as words or images) presented side by side. One stimulus is non-emotional, while the other is emotionally salient (e.g., threatening). After briefly presenting the stimulus pair (typically 500ms), a small dot (probe) appears in the location previously occupied by one of the stimuli. The participant's task is to indicate the placement of the probe as quickly and accurately as possible. Notably, Onie and Most (2022) provide evidence that emotion-induced blindness tasks assess emotion prioritization in attentional bias and thus help assess emotional information processing. Dot probe tasks, in contrast, were found to be relatively insensitive and unreliable indicators of emotion processing.

CONCLUSION

Using an emotion-induced blindness task, the present study found that higher attachment avoidance, but not attachment anxiety, predicted reduced target identification following threatening and conflict related images at an intermediate temporal lag. This pattern is consistent with a dual process account of avoidant attachment in which threat related cues capture attention early in processing before later disengagement. No evidence emerged for an anxiety related hypervigilance effect under the present conditions.

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REFERENCES

- Bowlby, J. (1982). *Attachment and loss* (Vol. 1, *Attachment*). Basic Books. (Original work published 1969).
- Chun, D. S., Shaver, P. R., Gillath, O., Mathews, A., & Jorgensen, T. D. (2015). Testing a dual-process model of avoidant defenses. *Journal of Research in Personality, 55*, 75–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2015.02.002>
- Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Buchner, A., & Lang, A.-G. (2009). Statistical power analyses using G*Power 3.1: Tests for correlation and regression analyses. *Behavior Research Methods, 41*, 1149–1160. <https://doi.org/10.3758/brm.41.4.1149>
- Fraley, R. C., Heffernan, M. E., Vicary, A. M., & Brumbaugh, C. C. (2011). The experiences in close relationships-relationship structures questionnaire: A method for assessing attachment orientations across relationships. *Psychological Assessment, 23*(3), 615–625. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0022898>
- Lang, P. J., Bradley, M.M., & Cuthbert, B.N. (2008). *International Affective Picture System (IAPS): Affective ratings of pictures and instruction manual*. Technical Report A-8. University of Florida, Gainesville, FL.
- Mikulincer, M., & Shaver, P. R. (2016). *Attachment in adulthood*. New York: Guilford Press.
- Mikulincer, M., & Shaver, P.R. (2019). Attachment orientations and emotion regulation. *Current Opinion in Psychology, 25*, 6–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2018.02.006>
- Most, S. B., Chun, M. M., Widders, D. M., & Zald, D. H. (2005). Attentional rubbernecking: Cognitive control and personality in emotion-induced blindness. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review, 12*(4), 654–661. <https://doi.org/10.3758/bf03196754>
- Niedenthal, P. M., Brauer, M., Robin, L., & Innes-Ker, A.H. (2002). Adult attachment and the perception of facial expression of emotion. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 82*, 419–433. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.82.3.419>
- Onie, S., & Most, S. B. (2022). On the relative sensitivity of spatial and nonspatial measures of attentional bias: Emotion-induced blindness, the dot probe, and gradations in ratings of negative pictures. *Emotion, 22*(8), 1942–1951. <https://doi.org/10.1037/emo0000855>
- Peirce, J. W., Gray, J. R., Simpson, S., MacAskill, M. R., Höchenberger, R., Sogo, H., Kastman, E., & Lindeløv, J. (2019). PsychoPy2: Experiments in behavior made easy. *Behavioral Research Methods, 51*(1), 195–203. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-018-01193-y>
- Peng, X., Gillath, O., Jiang, M., Wang, B., Zhang, J., & Wu, L. (2023). Attachment style and attention bias to emotional information: The moderating effect of stress, stimulus characteristics, and attention stage. *Journal of Personality. https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12891*
- Wang, L., Kennedy, B. L., & Most, S. B. (2012). When emotion blinds: A spatiotemporal competition account of emotion-induced blindness. *Frontiers in Psychology, 3*, 438. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2012.00438>
- Zhang, Q., Hou, Z. J., Fraley, R. C., Hu, Y., Zhang, X., Zhang, J., & Guo, X. (2021). Validating the Experiences in Close Relationships-Relationship Structures Scale among Chinese children and adolescents. *Journal of Personality Assessment, 104*(3), 347–358. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223891.2021.1947844>